

etc.) that have their own genetic material.

The aleurone grains may be regarded as a specific type of plastids (alongside with chloroplasts, chromoplasts, amyloplasts, proteoplasts, etc.). □

Genetic diversity in rice *Oryza sativa* L.

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Divergence analysis was performed to identify diverse genotypes for hybridization and to generate crosses that give transgressive segregants in later generations.

The parental divergence study used varieties released in Mekong Delta. Materials came from IRRI (21), India (3), Korea (1), Sri Lanka (1), and Vietnam (6).

The experiment was conducted at Omon in 1989 dry season, with 32 treatments in a randomized block design with three replications. Plots were 10 m², spacing was 15 × 20 cm.

Clustering (Mahalonobis D² statistics) was based on plant height, days to 50% flowering, panicle length, grains per panicle, unfilled grain percentage, effective tillers per plant, grain weight, and grain yield.

Table 1. Varieties partitioned into clusters on the basis of eight characters. Omon, Vietnam, 1989 dry season.

Cluster	Varieties
I	OM576, IR13240-10-1, IR25588-7-3-1, IR31868-64-2, IR19728, IR66, IR31802-48-2, OM296, IR17433-641-1, IR36, IR17434, IR9782-111-2, OM91, IR1352, IR39357-133-3, IR65, IR64, IR74, IR9129-192-2, IR21015-80-3, OM201, IR13240-10-1, OM620, IR4265-269-4-2
II	IR42, OM80, Bharain, Basmati 370 (mutant)
III	A69-1, IR48
IV	IR68
V	Basmati 370

Table 2. Average intracluster and intercluster D²-values, showing divergence of variety clusters. Omon, Vietnam, 1989 dry season.

Cluster	I	II	III	IV	V
I	7.1751	14.6391	16.5844	19.6446	21.3976
II		9.0341	15.7413	23.3252	14.0877
III			8.9537	10.9978	21.4578
IV				0.0000	27.1334
V					0.0000

The materials were grouped into five clusters by Tocher's method (Table 1). Clusters separated by the largest statistical distance (D²) show the maximum divergence (Table 2).

Plant height (frequency 8-43%) and days to 50% flowering (frequency 7-37%) contributed to divergence the most. □

Yield potential

Effect on rice yield of root damage to seedlings

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During droughts, uprooting of rice seedlings is difficult particularly in clay soils. Seedlings sustain severe root damage, in extreme cases losing almost all their roots. We evaluated the effect of different levels of root damage on yield in a field experiment during 1986 ahu (autumn). Six varieties and four levels of seedling root damage were

used in a split-plot design with three replications (see table). Plot size was 4 m².

Seedlings were pulled at 25 d after seeding and transplanted 29 May, 1 seedling/hill at 15- × 20-cm spacing. No fertilizer was applied.

There was no interaction between variety and root damage for any of the characters considered (see table). Seedlings with 50% roots removed did not differ from seedlings with intact roots in survival, yield attributes, and yield, but they flowered earlier. Seedlings with 98% roots removed by cutting at the bottom nodes and

Effect of seedling root damage and variety on yield, yield components, hill mortality, and flowering duration of rice. Titabar, India, 1986 autumn.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Hill mortality ^a (%)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle weight (g)	Days to 50% flowering
<i>Seedling root damage</i>					
Intact roots	2.4	24	287.1	0.88	92
50% removed	2.2	24	310.3	0.71	90
98% removed	1.7	35	232.2	0.78	94
100% removed	0.4	69	67.4	0.50	98
LSD (0.05)	0.4	7	40.4	0.20	1
<i>Variety</i>					
Pusa 2-21	1.9	38	201.5	0.81	96
IET6155	2.2	30	268.6	0.79	102
IET6148	1.6	32	230.5	0.70	100
IET7983	1.6	42	217.7	0.77	94
IET7617	1.5	46	204.9	0.67	90
Culture 1	1.3	39	222.5	0.56	80
LSD (0.05)	0.4	9	ns	ns	2

^aAngular transformed data.